

[white paper: pedagogical]

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The terms of a language with one constant, one binary function, and one 4-ary function have an odd number of symbols

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Abstract

We show using induction on complexity that all terms of a language with one constant, one binary function, and one 4-ary function have an odd number of symbols.

keywords: language, induction on complexity, first-order logic

The most updated version of this white paper is available at

<https://osf.io/ue32a/download>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5457880>

Introduction

1. This is a pedagogical white paper on *first-order logic*.
2. Our purpose is to discuss a result in [1] which is licensed under [2].
3. We use minimal notation but preserving all relevant mathematical information.

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Meta-linguistic symbols

4. $:=$ means that what is on the left is defined by what is on the right.
5. \equiv means that the strings on both sides are identical.
6. $a, b \vdash c$ means deduction of c from a, b .

Proposition

7.

$\mathcal{L} = \{0, f, g\} \rightarrow$ every \mathcal{L} -term has an odd number of symbols

8. $\mathcal{L} :=$ language
9. $0 :=$ constant symbol
10. $f :=$ binary function symbol
11. $g :=$ 4-ary function symbol

Proof of (7) by induction on complexity

12. $t :=$ \mathcal{L} -term
13. We need to prove that t has an odd number of symbols.

Case 1

14. $t \equiv 0$
15. t has 1 symbol.

Case 2

16. t is a variable.
17. t has 1 symbol.

Case 3

18. $t \equiv ft_1t_2$
19. $n :=$ number of symbols in t
20. Inductive hypothesis: *a term has an odd number of symbols.*
21. Let n_1 and n_2 be the number of symbols in t_1 and t_2 , respectively.
22. (20) \vdash n_1 and n_2 are odd numbers.
23. $n = n_1 + n_2 + 1$
24. (22), (23) \vdash n is odd.

Case 4

25. $t \equiv gt_1t_2t_3t_4$
26. This case is similar to Case 3. □

Open Invitation

Review, add content, and co-author this white paper [3,4].

*Join the **Open Mathematics Collaboration**.*

Send your contribution to mplobo@uft.edu.br.

Open Science

The **latex file** for this *white paper* together with other *supplementary files* are available in [5,6].

How to cite this paper?

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Agreement

All authors agree with [4].

References

[1] Leary, Christopher C., and Lars Kristiansen. *A friendly introduction to mathematical logic*, 2nd edition, 2015.

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